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University Students' Opinions on Translation Course for Special Purposes (Legal Translation Sample)

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Abstract

The need for translation, which is an important bridge in intercultural communication, is increasing day by day. In recent years, because of the development of economic, political, and cultural relations with the countries whose official language is Arabic, the interest in Arabic translation has increased. In this context, Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments have been opened at universities. In these departments, translation courses for students' ability to translate in different fields are also given in areas of specialization such as medical translation and legal translation. Since translations for areas of specialization have their own terminology, it brings various difficulties in the translation process. In this study, it was tried to determine the problems experienced in the process of legal translation by taking the opinions of the students who took the legal translation course in the Department of Arabic Translation and Interpretation at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University. In this context, 7 open-ended questions were asked to 15 students who took the course of legal translation in this department. Based on the answers given to these questions, the problems experienced by the students during the legal translation process were determined and suggestions were made for the solution of these problems.

Keywords: Translation, Legal Translation, Translation Departments, Arabic Translation

1. Introduction

Translation, which emerges with the need of communities speaking different languages to communicate with each other, increases its importance day by day. Translation, which is a bridge in the transfer of knowledge between societies, plays an important role in ensuring that societies get to know each other closely. Because societies speaking different languages provide each other through translation. In this context, it is possible to say that the globalizing world where the interaction between societies increases rapidly, the importance of translation increases as well. Yalçın (2015: p. 9) defines translation as an indispensable activity of the age, which plays a vital role in the life of societies and is an indispensable activity in the information exchange between societies, and the process of transferring the statements in one language to another language by providing equivalence in terms of meaning and style and the resulting product. Catford (1965: p.1) further considers translation as “an operation performed on languages: a process of substituting a text in one language for a text in another” is needed in every field from science to art and from literature to international relationships.”

In this context, it is possible to say that translation, which is a tool in intercultural knowledge transfer, takes place in every field. As a result of the use of translation in all areas of life, special purpose translations such as literary translation, legal translation, medical translation are done as well. Special-purpose translations are intended for a specific field and require the use of language for that field in the translation process. Training for special purpose translation is included in the curriculum of translation and interpretation departments of universities. Because it is necessary to have a command of the terminology of that field to translate in different fields. In this study, the opinions of university students on legal translation will be discussed.

1.1. Literature review

Language for specific purposes (LSP) courses are those in which the methodology, the content, the objectives, the materials, the teaching, and the assessment practices all stem from specific, target language uses based on an identified set of specialized needs Hyland (2002). further states that LSP courses should be designed for students targeting one professional or academic environment discipline. In this context, we can list the features of the special purpose translation courses in the translation and interpreting departments as follows:

- Designed to meet the needs of students in the relevant field
- It is intended for a specific field
- Focus on the appropriate language for the relevant field

Trace, Hudson, and Brown (2015, p.6) state that it is something of a misconception to view the development of an LSP course as different from the development of any other kind of language course. Certainly, there are different challenges and areas of focus, but LSP curriculum development, to a great extent, involves the same kinds of processes as any other language course. In this context, we can say that the process of preparing the curriculum of special purpose translation courses is not different from other courses, but only focuses on different points.

Translation is simply defined as the transfer from one language to another. However, it may not be appropriate to define legal translation in this way as it is one of the special purpose translation fields. Sarcevic (1997: p.13) states that it is a translation from one legal system into another – from the source legal system into the target legal system. Based on this, we can define legal translation as transferring from one system to another rather than from one language to another.

Cao (2007: p. 10-11) gives the following classification for purposes for legal translation:

- Legal translation for the normative purpose: authentic legal texts in bilingual and multilingual jurisdictions of domestic laws and international legal instruments and other laws
- Legal translation for the informative purpose: statutes, court decisions, scholarly works, and other types of legal documents
- Legal translation for legal or judicial purpose: statements of claims or pleadings, contracts and agreements, and ordinary texts such as business or personal correspondence, records, and certificates

According to this classification legal translation refers to the translation of texts used in law and legal settings, and it is used as a general term to cover both the translation of law and other communications in the legal setting (Cao: 2007 p. 25).

Legal translation, which is an important tool in the development of relations between countries, has brought developments in the field of legal translation with the developments between countries in recent years. Because with the development of relations between countries, the need for translations in the field of law has increased. Because countries need translation in this field to develop and maintain their relations with each other. This increases the importance of legal translation every day.

In order to meet the need for legal translation, legal translation courses are given in the translation and interpretation departments of universities. In this context, legal translation courses are given in Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Department of Arabic Translation, and Interpretation. These lessons are as follows:

Table 1: Legal Translations in Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University Arabic Translation and Interpretation Program Curriculum (Arapça Programı Müfredatı, 2021)

1. Year	
1. Semester	2. Semester
Legal Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)	Legal Translation II (Turkish-Arabic)
2. Year	
1. Semester	2. Semester
Legal Translation III (Arabic-Turkish)	Legal Translation IV (Turkish-Arabic)
3. Year	
1. Semester	
Legal Translation V	

According to this table, of legal translation is given in five semesters in the Department of Arabic Translation and Interpretation at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University. In this study, it was tried to determine the opinions of the students who took the legal translation course in the Department of Arabic Translation and Interpretation at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University.

1.2. Aim of Study

In the Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments of the universities, education is given to train students competent in the field of legal translation in Arabic-Turkish language pairs. Different terminology in legal and different legal systems bring various difficulties in the translation process. In this research, it is aimed that students who take legal translation courses in Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments of universities will improve themselves in this field. In this context, it is aimed to provide suggestions to increase the competence of the students in the field of legal translation.

2. Method

In the first step of the study, a literature review was conducted about legal translation. In order to determine the problems faced by the students in the legal translation process, open-ended questions were created by taking expert opinion. A seven-item open-ended question regarding the legal translation course was applied to 15 students who took a legal translation course in the Department of Arabic Translation at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University. The data obtained were categorized and examined, and evaluations were made on the difficulties they faced in legal translation and their solutions.

2.1. Sample

The universe of this research consists of students taking legal translation courses in Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments of universities. The sample of the study is composed of students taking legal translation course in Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Department of Arabic Translation, and Interpretation.

2.2. Data collection procedures

Answers were sought to seven basic open-ended questions used in the study, and students were asked to answer each question in detail:

1. What kind of method do you follow in the legal translation process and what are the difficulties you experience in this process?
2. If you have difficulties in the legal translation process, why do you think you have difficulties?
3. Which methods and techniques are used in legal translation courses?
4. Do you think the methods and techniques applied in the legal translation course are sufficient? If not enough, what are its shortcomings?
5. Is the teaching of the legal translation course efficient for you? If not, what are its shortcomings?
6. Are there any problems arising from emotional reasons (fear of making mistakes, anxiety, refraining from making mistakes) that negatively affect you during the legal translation process? If so, can you explain?
7. What kind of materials do you use in the legal translation course? Can you explain in detail?

2.3. Data analysis

Data collection procedures and data analysis can be combined under “Data collection and analysis.”

3. Results

Table 2: What kind of method do you follow in the legal translation process and what are the difficulties you experience in this process?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: I am **searching for** examples of the document which I translate. Then I create a translation draft. Then I find the meanings of the words and phrases from dictionaries. After that, I complete the process by translating it. I can say that the biggest difficulty I have experienced in Arabic legal translation is that Arab countries have different types of documents.

Participant 2: During the translation process, I usually take care to translate verbatim. The difficulty is that each country has its own local uses.

Participant 3: First I do the translation myself. Later in the lesson, I see my mistakes by comparing with the lecturer's translation. Not being able to remember legal terms or knowing where to start is one of my difficulties.

Participant 4: Since I think it is necessary to have knowledge in the field of law in the translation process, I try to get information in this field. In addition, I think that both languages should be mastered in the translation process. During this process, we faced a completely different jargon, so I had a hard time conveying the patterns and definitions of the source language to the target language.

Participant 5: I try to be systematic in this process. I keep the translations we have made, thinking that it will be useful in future translations. The difficulty I faced during the legal translation process was not being able to master the legal terms and concepts in legal language very well in my native language.

Participant 6: In the legal translation process, I first look at the content of the document and decide what course I should follow and translate it in general terms. The biggest challenge I faced in this process is the structure of the documents.

Participant 7: In legal translation, I first read the document and create in my head where to connect the sentence and where to start the translation. Then I start the translation based on the source text, find the words I do not know the meaning of and insert it into the translation. One of my biggest difficulties is that I am unfamiliar with the expressions used in legal texts.

Participant 8: The translation process often differs from text to text. If the sentences in the text are short, I translate them by considering the subject-verb harmony. However, if the sentences are long, I break the sentence and translate it. Then I combine these sentences. The most difficult point is to keep the flow of the text in both languages without distorting the meaning.

Participant 9: I am trying to translate by dividing the source text. Generally, I first determine the subject and predicate, placing all the remaining parts between these two elements in turn. One of my main difficulties is not being able to translate an expression I understand in the source language into the target language.

Participant 10: I am reading the text to be translated from beginning to end. Then I divide the text in certain places. Then I translate the places I divided. The use of grammatical structures and tenses in legal language in a different way is one of my difficulties.

Participant 11: In the legal translation process, I read the entire text or document once. Then I look at the meaning of the words I do not know. Then I try to translate using expressions in accordance with the content of the document or text. Special terms in the texts are at the top of my difficulties.

Participant 12: I pay attention to ensuring fluency in the text and using a language suitable for the text. I prefer the translation of phrases rather than word translation. Having different legal systems makes me difficult in the translation process.

Participant 13: I take care to translate according to the document type. It is difficult for me that the documents are diverse and contain unique words and phrases.

Participant 14: I prefer to translate after listening to the lesson. Because after the lesson I understand the translation better. The long texts make it difficult for me in the translation process.

Participant 15: While translating, I try to be impartial, to give the meaning precisely, and to use words in accordance with legal terminology. I am having trouble finding the right word while translating it into Turkish.

This item attempts to determine the path the students follow in the legal translation process and what problems they encounter. According to the data obtained, students use methods such as reading the text from beginning to end and determining where to connect it to the translation, benefiting from previous translations, using jargon suitable for the legal language by finding the equivalents of the words and phrases by dividing the text according to the length of the text or using expressions appropriate to the text in order to provide translation fluency as a whole. In addition, students face difficulties such as having different types of legal documents of Arab countries in legal translation, finding the right word in the translation process, being the texts quite long, having different legal systems and not being able to master legal concepts in the mother tongue.

Table 3: If you have difficulties in the legal translation process, why do you think you have difficulties?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: I can say that the biggest difficulty I have experienced in Arabic legal translation is that Arab countries have different types of documents. Because not seeing many of the documents and gradually mastering words and phrases makes translation difficult at first glance.

Participant 2: The difficulty is that each country has its own local uses. I often have a lack of which word is used instead of which word in local use.

Participant 3: Not being able to remember legal terms or knowing where to start is one of my difficulties. The reason for this may be that I have not mastered Arabic very much and I have not seen legal texts in such detail before.

Participant 4: During this process, I faced a completely different jargon, so I had a hard time conveying the patterns and definitions of the source language to the target language. I was having a hard time because of the lack of competence in the field of law, for example, being in between long and difficult sentences such as a power of attorney, and the specific language of contracts. Currently, it is difficult to find equivalents in translation from Turkish to Arabic.

Participant 5: I am having difficulties in the translation process because I am not able to master the legal terms and concepts in legal language very well in my native language.

Participant 6: The biggest challenge I faced in this process is the structure of the documents. Because I have difficulty in creating the document structure.

Participant 7: One of my biggest difficulties is that I am unfamiliar with the expressions used in legal texts. This is **because** we do not see such documents in normal life.

Participant 8: It is the most difficult point to be able to keep the flow of the text in a way that does not distort the meaning in both languages. This is because I have difficulties in the legal terms of the Arab culture, which we are just learning, while we are unfamiliar with these texts in Turkish.

Participant 9: One of my main difficulties is not being able to translate an expression that I understand in the source language into the target language. I think that the difficulties I experienced are caused by not knowing this jargon in general, my inadequate vocabulary and desire to be the best in translation.

Participant 10: The use of grammatical structures and tenses in legal language in a different way is one of my difficulties. This is because I do not know the tradition of texts and the culture of the area.

Participant 11: Special terms in the texts are at the top of my difficulties. I think I have a hard time finding the equivalent of the special terms used in translation.

Participant 12: Having different legal systems makes me difficult in the translation process. I have difficulty in translation since the laws and concepts used in legal systems are different.

Participant 13: I am challenged by the variety of documents and their unique vocabulary and phrases. This is because it is impossible for us to dominate all areas.

Participant 14: The length of the texts challenges me in the translation process. This is because I am afraid of translating long texts.

Participant 15: I am having trouble in finding the right word when translating it into Turkish, as I cannot master the legal terminology

This item tried to determine the reasons for the problems faced by the students in the process of legal translation. According to the data obtained, the reasons for the problems faced by the students in the process of legal translation are not able to master legal terminology, the differences in the laws and the usage of the legal systems, the inability to know the text tradition and the field culture, the insufficient vocabulary, the length of the text, not using legal terms in daily life.

Table 4: Which methods and techniques are used in legal translation courses?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: To consider both the meanings of the words and expressions in the document and their use in the country where the document belongs, to evaluate the uses and equivalents in the field of law and to form the document according to them.

Participant 2: Sending the text to the student beforehand and then translating it in the lesson with the student.

Participant 3: First we translate it ourselves, then we translate with our lecturer practically.

Participant 4: Document translation-based methods and techniques are used.

Participant 5: There is an interactive process in the lesson. The student prepares for the lesson by translating the document samples in the source language.

Participant 6: An interactive student-oriented method is followed in the lessons.

Participant 7: We translate from part to whole. We focus on the phrases in the text. We pay attention to the formal correctness and appropriateness of the text.

Participant 8: In the legal translation course, the first attempt is to create a translation competent. While providing this, the way of developing cultural, text, mother tongue and foreign language skills is followed for the translation competent which is acquired by creating theoretical background knowledge and undertakes the upper umbrella role.

Participant 9: In the legal translation course, the document we will translate is delivered to us before the lesson. Before the lesson, we try to translate the document with our own efforts. By comparing the translations, we made during the lesson, we translate the document again with our lecturer.

Participant 10: During the lesson, we generally exchange ideas, this method helps us find the most accurate and best sentence.

Participant 11: In legal translation lessons, methods such as question-answer technique, demonstration technique, observation technique, laboratory technique, and expression method are used.

Participant 12: In the lessons, our lecturer first gives us the right to speak in order for us to learn better and to eliminate the question marks in our minds, and then corrects our mistakes. It emphasizes important places and pays attention to the use of these expressions in subsequent documents in order for them to be permanent.

Participant 13: In the legal translation course, we learn the terms of the language in which the translation will be made, and after gaining knowledge on the subject, we perform our translations.

Participant 14: The method used in the lesson was based on the student seeing the document before the lesson and translating it as he/she understood it and showing where the student made a mistake during the lesson.

Participant 15: The document, whose translation is in question, is translated by offering translation alternatives with the contributions of lecturer and students, and then the translation, which is the most appropriate, is taken as basis.

This item tried to determine which methods and techniques were used in the legal translation course. According to the data obtained, we can say that methods and techniques such as translating the text first, learning the terms of the text to be translated with the lecturer, then translating the text and exchanging ideas about the translation of the text during the course.

Table 5: Do you think the methods and techniques applied in the legal translation course are sufficient? If not enough, what are its shortcomings?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: I would like to say that the course is sufficient as it provides us with the opportunity to translate different types of documents and learn different uses.

Participant 2: I am satisfied with the course. I would love to just let the lecturer show us more examples and explain how we should follow the path if we want to specialize in the future.

Participant 3: I think the methods and techniques used are sufficient. However, it may be useful for us to see more documents.

Participant 4: Quite enough. But in terms of the course (due to the differences in documents from country to country) it would be better to see more documents.

Participant 5: I think it is enough for me.

Participant 6: I think it is enough.

Participant 7: Considering the course time and opportunities, it is sufficient, but we see that this is not enough for professional life. As guides and experienced lecturers, I believe that our lecturers should shed light on us and give us the necessary work experience.

Participant 8: I think the methods we use have improved me a lot.

Participant 9: I find the course methods and techniques sufficient, and the duration of the course insufficient in terms of seeing different documents.

Participant 10: I think that the methods and techniques applied in the legal translation course are generally sufficient, but I think that the students should be guided more actively with translation studies in the applied part of the course after the theoretical knowledge part.

Participant 11: Although the method applied in the legal translation course is sufficient, additions can be made.

Participant 12: I think it is enough.

Participant 13: I think these methods are sufficient if the necessary relationship and communication is established between the student and the teacher.

Participant 14: I think it is enough.

Participant 15: I think it is sufficient because our lesson is generally based on the documents we will translate while performing this profession.

In this item, it has been tried to determine whether the methods and techniques used in legal translation are sufficient and if not, what are their shortcomings. Students generally think that the method and techniques used in the course are sufficient. However, in addition to this, the students stated that it would be more beneficial to show more examples of documents in the course, to make more applications and to guide the students in order to gain professional experience in this field.

Table 6: Is the teaching of the legal translation course efficient for you? If not, what are its shortcomings?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: I think that our systematic progress with the translation techniques and methods used in the course is sufficient to make the translation process effective.

Participant 2: The fact that students sometimes are so involved in translation, and this discourages me from listening to the lecture. The information given by the lecturer is very useful for me. I usually use that information both in the exam and when I translate myself.

Participant 3: It is a very efficient and favorite lesson for me.

Participant 4: It is one of my favorite lessons and it helps me a lot as I want to work in this field in the future.

Participant 5: Based on the number of students, I think it is efficient. Of course, if we had the opportunity to learn in smaller groups, this would also allow us to make more translations.

Participant 6: The legal translation course is extremely efficient for me.

Participant 7: It is efficient, but I think it can be more efficient.

Participant 8: The methods and techniques used in the legal translation course are very efficient for me. Of course, the study and repetition that the student has to do outside the classroom is also very important in this regard.

Participant 9: Especially in the distance education process, one of the lessons that were taught in the most efficient way for me was the legal translation course.

Participant 10: The teaching of the legal translation course is generally efficient for me, but at times, when the course continues monotonously, my mind gets tired, and I have difficulties in focusing.

Participant 11: Legal translation course is efficient for me, but some methods can be used to increase the efficiency of the course.

Participant 12: It is very productive for me. The only point I have trouble with is that some friends constantly ask questions during the lesson. This is their most natural right, but some questions can be really out of place. That's why I get distracted from time to time.

Participant 13: Both the documents sent by the teacher beforehand, and the documents translated in the course make the teaching of the course efficient in general.

Participant 14: When the lecturer does the explanation and analysis in the lesson, the teaching of the lesson is very efficient for me, but since many of our friends, other than our lecturer, express their opinions, my mind and knowledge get confused and I may have difficulties when listening to the lesson at that moment.

Participant 15: Yes, it is very efficient for me I think that many document translations and the phrases, terms and words that I learned from each document prepares me for the profession.

In this item, the students were asked whether the course of legal translation was efficient and, if not, what are its shortcomings. Students generally state that the lesson was efficient. However, in addition to this, students express that their motivation for the lesson decreases when they are very involved in the lesson and when the lesson continues monotonously.

Table 7: Are there any problems arising from emotional reasons (fear of making mistakes, anxiety, refraining from making mistakes) that negatively affect you during the legal translation process? If so, can you explain?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: Although I sometimes worry about making mistakes for legal translation, I prefer not to hesitate to make mistakes in general context and to convey the information I know. I consider making mistakes as a way to learn true translation and get new information.

Participant 2: Yes. I feel afraid of not giving exact meaning in translation and problems like If I cannot translate the names correctly and what is the equivalent in that country are very stuck in my mind.

Participant 3: Yes, I'm afraid of making mistakes in translation. The reason for this is that I have a lot of competitors and people who have developed themselves in this field. And, when I make mistakes, I can get negative results in my business life and put people in a difficult situation.

Participant 4: Of course, I have the fear of making mistakes in translation as everyone else.

Participant 5: Wouldn't it? I have said that the most important factor in legal translation is the accuracy of the information. Sometimes, misreading a letter or missing a zero in a contract can seriously harm us. We must be very meticulous. While observing all these, you are inevitably afraid of making mistakes in translation.

Participant 6: I have no emotional problems in the legal translation course.

Participant 7: I get nervous when I see documents with different structures.

Participant 8: Legal translation is the field I want to specialize in the future. Therefore, it is very important for me to learn this lesson well. This sometimes puts pressure on me.

Participant 9: There are two main reasons that negatively affect me in this process; The first is that I want the translation to be perfect from beginning to end, and the second is the worry of a mistake that may occur when translating in this area can have big consequences

Participant 10: Since legal translation is a field that does not accept making mistakes, the fear of making mistakes from time to time worries me and it delays my focus on the translation process.

Participant 11: I naturally have the worry of making mistakes in the legal translation process. Because our translation is usually a document and of course there is a sense of responsibility. For this reason, the worry of making mistakes is inevitable.

Participant 12: Making mistakes is not a problem for me, as I usually learn from mistakes I make.

Participant 13: Of course, we, as translator candidates, are experiencing emotional problems at this stage. This also varies according to the importance and length of the translated document.

Participant 14: Unfortunately, I have the problems written above. Because we have friends who are good at Arabic in the classroom, and they know most of the things. For this reason, I am reluctant to attend classes. This is not because of the fear of making mistakes, but because they are too advanced, and I feel too far behind in the classroom.

Participant 15: While trying to choose the most appropriate word and give the best meaning to the translation, I usually fear and worry about making mistakes.

In this item, students were asked if there are there any problems arising from emotional reasons (fear of making mistakes, anxiety, refraining from making mistakes) that negatively affect them during the legal translation process? According to the data obtained, we can say that the biggest problem faced by the students in the legal translation process is the worry of making mistakes.

Table 8: What kind of materials do you use in the legal translation course? Can you explain in detail?

Participant Opinions

Participant 1: In the lesson, if we are translating a similar document with the documents we have translated before, I will benefit from the documents we translated before. I use a dictionary.

Participant 2: I usually translate from the dictionary, but when it's not enough, I get support from sites like Wikipedia.

Participant 3: I keep the documents we translate in the lesson and work from them.

Participant 4: Due to the insufficiency of Turkish resources in this field, problems such as photocopying and therefore not collecting all materials in one hand during the term may occur.

Participant 5: The sine qua non of the legal translation course is a computer that will help us in translation process. In this context, it is important to transfer the documents and translation drafts we have made to digital memories.

Participant 6: We generally use legal documents in the legal translation course.

Participant 7: I do not use any materials other than the documents our lecturer gives us in the lesson.

Participant 8: Documents we previously translated, dictionaries and flashcards.

Participant 9: I use digital dictionaries in the translation process.

Participant 10: We usually use printed materials in the legal translation course. We use the texts determined in the weekly course schedule both as digital and printed materials in our lessons.

Participant 11: We usually use samples of legal documents in the lesson.

Participant 12: Documents, dictionaries, and document translation book.

Participant 13: We use the sample legal documents brought by the lecturer in the course.

Participant 14: I use digital dictionaries and printed dictionaries.

Participant 15: We use documents that can be translated in the field of legal translation.

In this item, it is tried to determine what kind of materials students use in the legal translation course. According to the data obtained, students use digital dictionaries and printed dictionaries in addition to the sample legal documents brought by the lecturer.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the opinions of the students regarding the legal translation course were taken, and the problems experienced by the students in the translation process were determined and suggestions were presented. This study, which aims to identify the problems encountered in the legal translation process and offer solutions, was carried out with 15 Participants. According to the data obtained, students usually encounter the following problems during the legal translation process:

- Worry about making mistakes in the translation process.
- Inability to master legal terminology.
- Differences in legal systems.
- Insufficient vocabulary.
- Not being able to master Arabic completely.
- Differences in legal documents from one Arab country to another.
- Legal field has its own unique terms.
- Legal texts are quite long.
- Not being able to fully master the concepts of the legal language in the mother tongue

Legal translation brings with it various difficulties, as it has a unique language and legal systems differ from country to country. According to the data obtained, the fact that the legal documents seen by the students are limited to the sample documents brought by the lecturer during the course reduces the opportunity for students to practice more legal document translations and see different types of documents. In addition to the documents seen in the course, students will be able to translate different documents outside of the course by obtaining sample documents from documents such as translation books, etc., which will enable students to develop in this field. In addition, students' familiarization with both the legal system in Arab countries and the Turkish legal system will facilitate the translation process.

Students' translation in a different field and being confronted with a different terminology will bring the worry of making mistakes. However, if the students master in target language and the source language, and translate in the field of law, it will contribute to the students to relieve these worries. Long legal texts may cause students to worry about the translation process. However, understanding the structure of legal texts and gaining familiarity with the texts can contribute to relieving the worry in the translation of long texts.

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